

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018

Deliverable D1.4

“Progress report no. 2”

Lead Beneficiary
FGB

Author(s)
F. Bonifazi, S. Ottomano, L. Ruggieri, A. Landi, A. Didio, B. Ojo, I. Mavridis, W. Atoyebi, K. Price, M. Brito, C. Lederer, P. Kountouris, C. Stephanou, S. Scott, P. Milligan, and PDB Inusa

Revision date
11/03/2024

Start date
01/01/2019
Duration
70 months
Project Coordinator
Fedele Bonifazi
FONDAZIONE PER LA RICERCA
FARMACOLOGICA GIANNI
BENZI onlus (FGB)

Dissemination Level	
PU = Public	<input type="checkbox"/>
CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
CI = Classified Information (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	<input type="checkbox"/>

Reference WP: WP1 – Scientific Coordination and Project Management
Reference Activity: Task 1.1 Scientific coordination

Index

1. List of authors
2. General Progress of the action
 - 2.1. Progress of the action during the period covered by this report
 - 2.2. General scientific progress of the action during the period covered by this report
 - 2.2.1. Work Package 1 “Scientific Coordination and Project Management”
 - 2.2.2. Work Package 2 “Implementing eHealth technologies to support a Newborn screening programme in African countries and Lebanon”
 - 2.2.3. Work Package 3 “Improving laboratory diagnostics and quality assurance systems for population screening”
 - 2.2.4. Work Package 4 “Newborn SCD screening, screening for neurocognitive complications, clinical care and antibiotic prophylaxis”
 - 2.2.5. Work Package 5 “Enhancement of SCD management through training in molecular diagnostic techniques and Genetic Counselling for haemoglobinopathies and performance of epidemiological and genetic research”
 - 2.2.6. Work Package 6 “Training and support for clinical research”
 - 2.2.7. Work Package 7 “Dissemination and Communication”
3. Corrective Measures
 - 3.1. Delays accumulated in the secondments / activities / deliverables foreseen in the Grant Agreement and the measures taken to oversee them
 - 3.2. Potential risks identified and suggested approaches to mitigate them
4. Ethical Issues
5. Additional information

General Progress of the action

The overall objective of the ARISE consortium is to provide the platform for researchers in Africa, EU, Lebanon and USA to collaborate in training and research activity to implement newborn screening and the comprehensive management of sickle cell disease. This report describes activities conducted in from 1st February 2020 to 31st October 2023.

Remarkably, the following achievements are highlighted for this reporting period:

- Full implementation of secondments. This included the development of contingency measures to mitigate travel restrictions due to the pandemics and increased cost of life, especially in UK.
- The planning, conduct and expansion of survey-based prospective studies aimed at mapping SCD facilities in concerned countries and patients & healthcare professionals' needs.
- Virtual lectures delivered in the framework of the online Virtual Teaching Programme to balance out secondments' suspension due to the pandemics. The ARISE virtual Teaching Programme has been able to deliver online more than 40 lectures spanning over 8 different themes and capturing the interest of nearly 700 attendees. The programme granted more than one thousand and one hundred CPD credits. ARISE also organised and hosted 5 webinars with more than 500 attendees.
- The UK NEQAS external quality assurance for NBS programme have been launched in Kaduna and Kafanchan states as part of ASH Consortium on Newborn Screening in Africa (CONSA) an international network that seeks to demonstrate the benefits of newborn screening and early interventions for children with Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) in sub-Saharan Africa.
- The development and adoption of laboratory Protocols for population screening for SCD/Thalassemia and national prevention policies are in development.
- Training implemented in the following areas: molecular diagnostic, laboratory testing and patients' counselling. We have undertaken research activities in epidemiology and assess policies for SCD management in partner countries.
- Virtual and face-to-face training on epidemiology, statistics, data analysis and publication.
- Implementation of communication and dissemination initiatives to raise awareness of the project, its activities and outcomes and facilitate knowledge sharing and translation into practice.

For all project activities, compliance with regulatory and ethical requirements at EU and country level has been granted thanks to the continuous oversight from Work Package 8. Training and support have been provided to all secondees.

The promotion of cooperation between African, US, and European researchers will ease the deployment of those interventions – including newborn screening (NBS), comprehensive care and self-management programmes for Sickle-Cell Disease (SCD) – able to reduce mortality and morbidities in early childhood and improve the overall disease outcome.

Moreover, several results are being achieved and potential impacts are being verified:

1. Staff exchanges improve researchers' skills
2. The project is developing a sustainable, context-based and comprehensive plan for SCD NBS in Sub-Saharan Africa and Lebanon, which considers also sociocultural factors
3. ARISE is developing a Community Stakeholder Engagement (CSE) strategy with communication with both internal & external stakeholders, initiatives to raise awareness of the project, its activities and outcomes and brand identity promotion.

The document includes a detailed description of activities and progresses per single work package, the corrective measures to oversee any delays in secondments / activities / deliverables, ethical issues and the updated table of potential risks.